

THE PRINCIPLE OF A HEALTHY DIRECTION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The idea of strengthening human health permeates the entire system of physical education. The following provisions follow from the principle of health-improving orientation of physical education.

Keywords: responsibility, physical education, physical culture, pedagogical control, long-term results, applicability.

1) Responsibility to the state for improving the health of those who exercise. Physical culture organizations, physical education teachers, coaches (as opposed to a doctor) deal, as a rule, with healthy people. They are responsible to the state not only for maintaining the health of those who go in for gymnastics, sports, games and tourism, but also for strengthening it;

2) Obligation and unity of medical and pedagogical control. Exercise is a remedy that gives a health-improving effect only when used correctly. In this regard, it is necessary to take into account the biological characteristics of age, sex and the state of health of those engaged in physical exercises. Systematic medical and pedagogical control presupposes strict consideration of these features. It should always be borne in mind that neither a teacher, even a well-trained one, nor the student himself can fully and in time notice the changes that occur in the body under the influence of physical exercises. A doctor comes to the rescue.[1,20]

Medical supervision of those engaged in is mandatory for all organizations that carry out work on physical culture. However, medical supervision should not be limited only to the statement of changes occurring in the human body. Along with the indicators of special pedagogical observation, the data of medical control are those

objective phenomena by which we can judge the positive or negative influence of physical exercises, change and improve the methods of physical education.[2,65]

The principle of the health-improving orientation of the domestic system of physical education of the daily creative community of a doctor, teacher and the student himself. If the practitioner feels a deterioration in health, and the doctor confirms this by analysis, then he should move away from intensive sports and be content with physical exercise as a remedy.

The doctor and the teacher are obliged, on the basis of taking into account the changes on the basis of taking into account the changes occurring in the body of the practitioner under the influence of physical exercises, to foresee the possible long-term results of these lessons.[3,85]

In conclusion, we can conclude that the meaning of this principle lies in the obligatory achievement of the effect of strengthening and improving human health. This principle obliges:

1. defining the specific content of the means and method of physical education, it is imperative to proceed from their health-improving value as an obligatory criterion;

2. to plan and regulate training loads depending on the gender, age and level of fitness of the student;

3. to ensure the regularity and unity of medical and pedagogical control in the process of assignments and competitions;

4. Make extensive use of the healing forces of nature and hygienic factors. Thus, as follows from the above, the main purpose of the general principles of physical education is as follows:

- firstly, to the creation of the most favorable conditions and opportunities for achieving the goal and solving the problems of physical education;

- secondly, to unite the general orientation of the physical education process (versatility, applicability, health improvement);

- thirdly, to the definition of the main ways that guarantee the achievement of positive results of physical education and the ways of their implementation in practice.[4,152]

No one can match the transformative power of physical culture and sports. This strength makes the awkward dexterous, the slow - fast, the weak - strong, always complaining of fatigue - hardy, the sickly - healthy. Good physical fitness allows you to quickly master new complex industrial professions; it also became one of the decisive factors in the training of pilots, cosmonauts, and the military.

Physical culture and sports contribute to the development of intellectual processes - attention, accuracy of perception, memorization, reproduction, imagination, thinking, improve mental performance. Healthy, hardened, well-physically developed young

men and women, as a rule, successfully perceive the educational material, get less tired in the classroom at school, and do not miss classes due to colds.

Physical education is also the most important means of forming a person as a person. Physical exercise allows you to multifaceted influence on the consciousness, will, on the moral character, character traits of boys and girls. They cause not only significant biological changes in the body, but to a large extent determine the development of moral convictions, habits, tastes and other aspects of the personality that characterize the spiritual world of a person.

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